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ClairCity - Citizen Led Air pollution Reduction in Cities

D2.3 ClairCity social media and online presence

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Deliverable 2.3: Website and wider social media presence

ClairCity will work across six cities in Europe to engage the public on issues of air pollution, carbon emissions and the future of their cities and regions. Core to the project are a set of innovative tools that will allow city residents to participate in understanding the problem, visioning the future and backcasting to achieve results for their city.

To promote ClairCity across a broad range of residents in each partner city and beyond, we are running a suite of online and social media tools. We have set up accounts on relevant platforms, and project partners will be collaborating to manage the use and development of online dissemination.

Website

Our website is www.claircity.eu This initial build provides our core project information to establish an online presence and create an initial, accessible site for ClairCity. A fully functional site, complete by October 2016 (M6), will contain Portuguese, English, Slovenian, Polish and Italian sections to incorporate visitors from our partner cities and beyond. It will host more detailed information on our project design and information on future outputs.

The website links to our social media platforms on Twitter and Facebook.

Social media

Our Twitter handle is @claircity <https://twitter.com/ClairCity> We are currently focused on building institutional and project associate links through Twitter. As the project incorporates more public facing elements over time, Twitter will become useful for these engagements too.

We have a publicly accessible Facebook page: ClairCity <https://www.facebook.com/ClairCity/> This will be the host for organizing English language events and promotions. As we launch activities in multiple countries we will develop mirror events to cater for all language requirements.

